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**PROBLEMS OF FARMERS WITH SPECIAL
REFERENCE TO UDUPI DISTRICT****Fathima Jabina*, K Swathi Shet*, Jableen****

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Abstract

Agriculture is one of the most important pillars of the Indian economy. The science and practice of farming including cultivation of the soil for the growing of crops and the rearing of animals provide food, wool and other products. Rural farmers account for the greater part of the population of any developing country such as India. The history of Indian agriculture dates back to 10000 years. Indian agriculture began during 9000 BC as a result of early cultivation of plants and domestication of crops and animals. The middle ages in India saw irrigation channels that reached a new level of sophistication. Land and water management systems were developed with objective of providing uniform growth. The agricultural sector employed 8.2 per cent of the total workforce in India, and despite a steady decline of its share in the GDP, it still remains the largest economic sector. Agricultural development is one of the most talked about issues as a major portion of our population is still engaged with the agricultural industry. The widespread modernization of agriculture, development of many modern techniques and improvement in farm productivity all are the basic characteristics of agricultural development. Since the beginning years of economic development, it has been one of the main drivers of growth of the economy as it supplies was a major source of raw materials to most of the manufacturers. To examine the different innovative measures adopted by different social groups for agricultural development in the district at block level. Agricultural extension services can and should play an important role in addressing many of these challenges.

Key words: Agricultural production, Growth, Technology, changes, Farm, Crops.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Agriculture plays a pivotal role in the Indian economy. Although its contribution to gross domestic product (GDP) is now around on sixth, it provides employment to 8.2 per cent of the Indian workforce.

Due to this reason most of the strategies of development even with its focus on different domains often emphasize upon rapid agriculture development in general and its modernisation in particular. Is a person engaged in agriculture, raising living organisms for food or raw materials The term usually applies to people who do some combination of raising field crops, orchards, vineyards, poultry, or other livestock. A farmer might own the farmed land or might work as a labourer on land owned by others, but in advanced economies, a farmer is usually a farm owner, while employees of the farm are known as farm workers, or farmhands. However, in the not so distant past, a farmer was a person who promotes or

improves the growth of (a plant, crop, etc.) by labour and attention, land or crops or raises animals.

Rural farmers or farmers are those who live in rural areas and fully depend on agriculture and its allied activities for their survival. But the problems of rural farmer are a major barrier in economic development. Therefore governments of developing countries have a major responsibility of ensuring that there is adequate rural development in their various communities and local governments which would lead to effective and efficient.

Poverty refers to a situation when people are deprived of basic necessities of life. It is often characterized by inadequacy of food, shelter and clothes. In other words, poverty refers to a state of privation where there is a lack of essential needs for subsistence.

Agricultural system not only supply food and animal protein but also fosters the utilization of natural resources in a sustainable manner (CGIAR, 1995). When the rural farmer lack access to knowledge and information that would help them achieve maximum agricultural yield, they are not only grope in dark but are driven to the urban centres in search of formal employment, as the only option for survival (Munyua, 2000; Blait, 1996) pointed out that the least expensive input for improved rural agricultural development is adequate access to knowledge and information in areas of new agricultural technology, early warning systems(drought, pests, diseases etc), improved seedlings, fertilizer, credit market prices etc. There have been short-comings of traditional print and library methods (Van and Fortier, 2000) of providing such agricultural information to rural farmers who are generally illiterate and relatively remote from sources of information.

In Assam around 8.2% of the state's population relies on agriculture as farmers or as agricultural labour. But almost all the farmers faces many problems like poverty, lack of knowledge about modern technology, illiteracy etc. In my study area Lowphulabori village under the Raha Block Development Area of Nagaon District of Assam, agricultural labours are pertaining to 3/4 of the total labour force. Agricultural labour and farmers in this area still remain serfdom or slavery system. Their income, standard of living, social status is very low. Increase the number of rural farmer in this study area due to increasing the size population, decline of cottage and village industries, evictions of small farmers, uneconomic holdings, growing indebtedness, deforestation, growth of capitalist farming etc. As a result the farmer of this area faces many problems such as poverty, lack of knowledge, about modern technology, lack of knowledge about market demandable agricultural.

BENEFITS OF AGRICULTURE

1. Land :

Conservation agriculture improves soil structure the soil against erosion and nutrient losses by maintaining a permanent soil cover and minimizing soil disturbance. Furthermore, CA practices enhance soil organic matter (SOM) levels and nutrient availability by utilizing the previous crop residues.

2. Labour:

Because land under no-till is not cleared before planting and involves less weeding and pest problems following the establishment of permanent soil cover /crop rotations, farmers in Ghana reported a 22% saving in labour associated with maize production.

3. Water:

Conservation agriculture requires significantly less water use due to increased infiltration and enhanced water holding capacity from crop residues left on the soil surface.

4. Nutrients:

Soil nutrient supplies and cycling are enhanced by the biochemical decomposition of organic crop residues at the soil surface that are also vital for feeding the soil microbes.

5. Soil biota:

Insect pests and other disease causing organisms are held in check by an abundant and diverse community of beneficial soil organisms, including predatory wasps, spiders, nematodes, springtails, mites and beneficial bacteria and fungi, among other species.

6. Economic benefits:

Farmers using CA technologies typically report higher yields (up to 45-48% higher) with fewer water, fertilizer and labour inputs, thereby resulting in higher overall farm profits.

7. Environmental benefits:

Conservation agriculture represents an environmentally-friendly set of technologies. Because it uses resources more efficiently than conventional agriculture, these resources become available for other uses, including conserving them for future generation.

8. Equity considerations:

Conservation agriculture also has the benefit of being accessible to many small-scale farmers who need to obtain the highest possible yields with limited land area and inputs.

9. Active role for farmers:

As with any new agricultural technology, CA methods are most effective when used with skilful management and careful consideration of the many agroecological factors affecting production on any given farm or field.

10. NEED FOR THE STUDY:

- To know the how many people's are doing agriculture in Udupi and North Canara District
- To know the knowledge regarding new agricultural technologies.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To know the income and productivity of the farmers.
2. To create awareness among farmers about credit facilities for agriculture in the nearby financial institution.
3. To examine the different innovation measures adopted by different social groups from agricultural development in the district at the block level.

IMPORTANCES OF AGRICULTURE:

Agriculture has its own importance. They are discussed in under:

1. Source of Livelihood

The main source livelihood of many people is agriculture. Approximately 70% of the people directly rely on agriculture as a mean of living. This percentage in agriculture

is as a result of none development of non-agricultural activities to absorb the fast – growing population.

2. Contribution to National revenue

Agriculture is the main source of national income for most developing countries. However, for the developed countries, agriculture contributes a smaller percentage to their national income.

3. Supply of Food as well as Fodder

Agricultural sector provides fodder for domestic animals, Cow provides people with milk which is a form of protective food. Moreover, livestock also meets people's food requirements.

4. Significance to the International Trade

Agricultural products like sugar, tea, rice, spices, tobacco, coffee etc. Constitute the major items of exports of countries that rely on agriculture. If there is smooth development practice of agriculture, imports are reduced while export increases considerably.

5. Marketable surplus

The growth of agricultural sector contributes to marketable surplus. Many people engage in manufacturing, mining as well as other non-agricultural sector as the nation develops. All these individuals rely on food production that they might meet from the nation's marketable surplus.

6. Source of Raw Material

The main source of raw materials to major industries such as cotton and jute fabric, sugar, tobacco, edible as well as non-edible oils is agriculture. Moreover, many other industries such as processing of fruits as well as vegetables and rice husking get their raw material mainly from agriculture.

7. Significance in Transport

Bulks of agricultural products are transported by railways and roadways from to factories. Mostly, internal trade is in agricultural product.

8. Foreign Exchange Resources

The nation's export trade depends largely on agricultural sector. This demonstrates that agriculture products also continue to be important source of earning a country foreign exchange.

9. Great Employment Opportunities

Construction of irrigation schemes, drainage system as well as other such activities in the agricultural sectors is important as it provides large employment opportunities.

10. Economic Development

Since agriculture employs many people it contributes to economic development. As a result, the national income level as well as people's standard of living is improved.

11. Source of saving

Development in agriculture may also increase savings. The rich farmers we see today started saving particularly after green revolution. This surplus quantity may be invested further in the agriculture sector to develop the sector.

12. Food security

A stable agricultural sector ensures a nation of food security. The main requirement of any country is food security.

SOURCES OF DATA:

The present study is mainly based on the available primary data collected from the A Study on Problems of farmers with special reference to Udupi district. The period of April 2019 were considered for the study.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The research paper is based on both primary and secondary data. In this research paper, the primary data was collected through face to face interaction of the farmers. In this research paper, recommendations and conclusions are based on primary data. The paper is based on investigation for the present research. The main role of investigation is based on the new creative ideas.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:**1. PURPOSE OF FARMING**

	SUBSISTANCE	COMMERCIAL	TOTAL
FARMERS	26	24	50

INTERPRETATION:

From the above table, out of 50 farmers, 26 farmers are growing products for subsistence purposes remaining 24 farmers are growing the products for commercial purposes.

2. TYPES OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS

	PADDY	ARKNET	CASHEW	COCONUT	RUBBER	TOTAL
FARMERS	36	4	0	10	0	50

INTERPRITATION:

Frome the above table, out of 50 farmers 36 are growing paddy, 4 farmers are growing ark nut, and 10 farmers are growing coconut.

3 REVENUE FROM AGREICULTURAL ACTIVITIES?

	BELOW 50000	50000-100000	100000-200000	200000-300000	TOTAL
FOREMERS	38	11	1	0	50

INTERPRITATION:

From the above chart the majority of the agriculturist yields below 50000 of revenue for a year (38).

4. AGRICULTURAL CREDIT FACILITY

	BORROW FROM FINANCIAL INSTITUTION	BORROW FROM MONEY LENDER	BORROW FROM OTHER	TOTAL
FARMERS	22	15	13	50

INTERPRITATION:

Frome the above, table financial institutions are the major fund supplier for the farmers.

5. DO YOU HAVE MARKETING FACILITIES?

	YES	NO	TOTAL
FARMERS	25	25	50

INTERPRITATION:

Frome the above table only half of the farmers have marketing facility, remaining half farmers are not get sufficient marketing facility to market their product.

6. DO YOU HAVE STOREAGE FACILITIES?

	YES	NO	TOTAL
FARMERS	20	30	50

INTERPRITATION:

Frome the above table out of 50 respondents, only 20 are having storage facility, remaining 30 farmers are not have storage facility.

7. DO YOU HAVE GOOD TRANSPOTATION FACILITIES?

	YES	NO	TOTAL
FARMERS	19	31	50

INTERPRITATION:

Frome the above table, out of 50 farmers only 19 farmers are getting a good transportation facility, remaining 31 farmers are not get sufficient transportation facility.

8. ARE YOU GETTING FINACIAL SUPPORT OF GOVERNMENT?

	YES	NO	TOTAL
FARMERS	11	39	50

INTERPRITATION:

Frome the above table, only 11 formers are getting financial support to the Government, remaining 39 farmers are not got any financial support to the government.

9. HAVE YOU GOT FAIR PRICE FOR PRODUCT?

	YES	NO	TOTAL
FARMERS	10	40	50

Frome the above table, out of 50 farmers only 10 farmers are get a fair price for their product, remaining 40 farmers are not get a fair price for their product.

10. DO YOU HAVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY BASED MARKETING FACILITIES?

	YES	NO	TOTAL
FARMERS	8	42	50

INTERPRITATION:

Frome the above table, out of 50 farmers only 8 farmers are get a information to technology based marketing facility, remaining 42 farmers are not get a information to technology based marketing facility.

11. DO YOU HAVE LACK OF IRRIGATION FACILITY?

	YES	NO	TOTAL
FARMERS	16	34	50

INTERPRITATION:

Frome the above table, out of 50 farmers only 16 farmers are get a good irrigation for their agriculture, remaining 34 farmers are not get a sufficient irrigation for their agriculture.

12. DO YOU GET ADEQUATE PROFIT?

	YES	NO	TOTAL
FARMERS	11	39	50

INTERPRETATION:

Frome the above table, out of 50 farmers only 11 farmers are get a adequate profit fore their agricultural product, but remaining 39 farmers are not get a adequate profit for their agricultural product .

SUGGESTIONS:

Based on the survey findings,

- Department of Agriculture must give a relevant information about new technology, transportation facility etc.
- Department o Agriculture must to promote the farmers to sale their product.
- Also Government take nasusury mashers to overcome the problem of money lender in the rural aria by extending the banking facilities and expansion of bank branches.

CONCLUSION:

On the basis of the above study we can say that the chronic poverty, illiteracy, lack of mechanisation, scarcity of HYU inputs, lack of capital formation, flood and drought, poor agricultural marketing facilities, lack of knowledge about demandable crops or more appropriately the absence of commercialization of agriculture sector are the main problems of

the rural farmers. Small farmers are an important component in society. Now it is time to focus on social economical problem of these farmers & try to find the solution to the problem. In above study farmers strongly demanding pension scheme only for food security not for luxurious life.

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